

A NEW APPROACH FOR LAMINATE DELAMINATION

O. ALLIX, L. DAUDEVILLE, P. LADEVÈZE
(Laboratoire de Mécanique et Technologie
ENS de Cachan / CNRS / Univ. P. et M. Curie, Cachan, France)

ABSTRACT

A new approach for laminate delamination based upon Damage Mechanics is proposed. Deteriorations such as fiber ruptures, matrix and interface degradations are introduced. A computation method for laminated plates with an initially circular and possibly loaded hole is presented. The proposed numerical treatment for this non-linear three-dimensional problem leads to a reasonable cost. Simulations are given. In addition, a simplified method for straight edges is also proposed. It uses elastic computations and criteria based on Damage Mechanics.

INTRODUCTION

In the design of laminate composite structures, delamination is a major mode of ruin that must be taken into account. This phenomenon which consists in the debonding of layers, appears in the vicinity of the edges of structures. This is due to the three-dimensional stress state in these regions, which may lead to high tensile or shear stresses on the interface of two adjacent layers. In the analysis of this phenomenon, distinction is made between an initiation phase and a propagation phase of an existing delaminated area. At present the simulation of both phases relies on the hypothesis of a perfect bonding between elastic layers. The analysis of initiation is quite qualitative, a more or less important tendency is assigned to different stacking sequences. Fracture Mechanics, of common use for metallic materials, is then applied for the study of the propagation of an existing delamination.

The proposed approach is the Damage Mechanics of composite laminates^{2, 3, 7, 9}, i.e the modelization at a structural analysis scale of gradual degradation phenomena in a material such as T300-914 due to the occurrence and the development of micro-cracks and micro-voids. This approach allows an accurate prediction of both the initiation and the propagation of delamination with a single model which considers the degradations of (i) the layers i.e fiber ruptures, transverse micro-cracking of the matrix, deterioration in the fiber-matrix bond, and (ii) the degradations of the interfaces between layers.

Using Fracture Mechanics in the prediction of delamination appears as a simplified tool as shown by some results presented below.

A first study¹ deals with the problem of delamination at the edge of an initially circular hole. It takes the degradation evolution in the laminate into account through the introduction of two elementary mechanical constituents: the layer and the interface. Since a thorough knowledge of the behaviour of these mechanical constituents is required, a theoretical and experimental study has been carried out in collaboration with the Aérospatiale company for the T300-914 and IM6-914 laminates^{2, 3, 7}. The layer model includes anisotropic unilateral damage and elastic-plastic behaviour. At a structural level, the computation of delamination initiation and growth leads to a non-linear three-dimensional evolution problem. This analysis can nevertheless be restricted to the vicinity of edges where three-dimensional effects are significant. The computation is kept between sensible limits by using (i) a new approach for non-linear structural computation i.e the "large time increment method" proposed by P. Ladevèze⁴, and (ii) a semi analytical method which requires the solution of two-dimensional problems only, due to the particular geometry of the edge. Results are presented which show the practicability and efficiency of this approach.

This study, takes precisely the degradations into account and can be used as a reference for delamination simulations, it is nevertheless of expensive use for parametered computations.

A simplified method⁵ to study delamination in the vicinity of a straight edge is also presented. The composite laminate is modelized as a stacking of elastic layers bonded by elastic and damageable interfaces. For an existing delamination area at each interface, the elastic problem is solved by an iterative technique that

reduces to separated and parallel computations of the different layers. Following this elastic computation, characteristic quantities are proposed ; by comparison with critical values and with Wohler's curves for the fatigue loadings, they allow to evaluate the damage and to follow the degradation evolution. The growth of an existing delamination area is studied with Fracture Mechanics.

MODELIZATION OF THE COMPOSITE LAMINATE BEHAVIOUR

The Damage concept introduced by Kachanov is defined as the progressive deterioration of loaded materials due to the initiation and the growth of micro-cracks. The Damage Mechanics for composite laminates is the modelization of these phenomena at a structural analysis scale. At this level the composite can be reduced to a stacking of elementary constituents :

- a homogeneous single layer in the thickness
- an interface which is a two-dimensional medium bonding two adjacent layers and which depends on their relative orientations.

In the same way as Hashin ⁸, the failure mode of each constituent is taken into account through a multi-criterion approach. This method has been developed by P. Ladevèze and al. 2, 3, 7, 9.

1. The single layer modelization.

Outside brittle fractures in the fiber direction N_1 , the main damage occurring in layers is due to micro-cracks of the matrix, which are parallel to N_1 , and degradations of fiber-matrix bond. The single layer damage is anisotropic and lies on the modification of the transverse E_2 and shear G_{12} moduli. The damages due to the

σ_{13} , σ_{23} , σ_{33} normal to the layer stress components are taken into account in the interface modelization. The strain energy of the damaged material is written by splitting up the transverse tensile and compressive energies due to the uni-lateral damage occurring in this material :

$$E_D = \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{\sigma_{11}^2}{E_1^0} + \frac{\langle -\sigma_{22} \rangle_+^2}{E_2^0} + \frac{\sigma_{33}^2}{E_3^0} \right] - \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{\nu_{12}^0}{E_1^0} + \frac{\nu_{21}^0}{E_2^0} \right) \sigma_{11} \sigma_{22} + \left(\frac{\nu_{13}^0}{E_1^0} + \frac{\nu_{31}^0}{E_3^0} \right) \sigma_{11} \sigma_{33} \right. \\ \left. + \left(\frac{\nu_{23}^0}{E_2^0} + \frac{\nu_{32}^0}{E_3^0} \right) \sigma_{22} \sigma_{33} \right] + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\langle \sigma_{22} \rangle_+^2}{(1-d') E_2^0} + \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{\sigma_{12}^2}{(1-d) G_{12}^0} + \frac{\sigma_{13}^2}{G_{13}^0} + \frac{\sigma_{23}^2}{G_{23}^0} \right]$$

The upperscript ⁰ means initial elastic modulus, the brackets denote the positive part, d and d' are two scalar damage variables. With respect to dissipation, the d and d' associated variables are :

$$Y_d = \frac{\partial E_D}{\partial d} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\sigma_{12}^2}{(1-d)^2 G_{12}^0} ; Y_{d'} = \frac{\partial E_D}{\partial d'} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\langle \sigma_{22} \rangle_+^2}{(1-d')^2 E_2^0}$$

A. Damage evolution modelization

With respect to the experimental results, the modelization we propose is associated with :

$$Y|_t = \sup_{|t' \leq t} [2Y_d + 2bY_{d'}]$$

Y is the quantity which governs damage evolution and fracture, b is a material constant. In order to describe the evolution of d and d', the following standard modelization is used :

$$d' = \frac{\langle Y - Y_0 \rangle_+}{Y_c} \quad \text{if } d' < 1 \text{ otherwise } d' = 1$$

$$d = \frac{\langle Y - Y_0 \rangle_+}{Y_c} \quad \text{if } d < 1 \text{ otherwise } d = 1$$

B. Plasticity

The matrix is slightly viscoplastic, but only plasticity is taken into account in a first step. The experiments show that damage and plasticity are coupled through the effective quantities $\bar{\sigma}$ and $\bar{\epsilon}_p$ ^{2 6}. The hardening is assumed isotropic.

2. Interface modelization

The interface is a zero thickness medium which ensures stress and displacement transfers from one ply to another. The (N_1, N_2) axes are the bisectors of the fiber directions. The displacement discontinuities are :

$$[U] = U^+ - U^- = [U_1] N_1 + [U_2] N_2 + [U_3] N_3$$

In a first step, the interface is assumed to be elastic and damageable. This modelization will be completed through comparisons between computations and experimental tests, this is a further difficulty. The energy per unit area is written as follows :

$$E_D = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\langle -\sigma_{33} \rangle^2}{k^o} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\langle \sigma_{33} \rangle^2}{(1-d) k^o} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\sigma_{32}^2}{(1-\gamma_2 d) k_2^o} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\sigma_{13}^2}{(1-\gamma_1 d) k_1^o}$$

γ_1, γ_2 : constant parameters

k^o, k_1^o, k_2^o : elastic parameters of the interface

$k^o, k_1^o, k_2^o \rightarrow +\infty$ for a perfect interface.

The d associated variable is Y_d :

$$Y_d = \frac{\partial E_D}{\partial d} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\langle \sigma_{33} \rangle^2}{(1-d)^2 k^o} + \gamma_2 \frac{\langle \sigma_{32} \rangle^2}{(1-d)^2 k_2^o} + \gamma_1 \frac{\langle \sigma_{13} \rangle^2}{(1-d)^2 k_1^o} \right)$$

Damage evolution is described by : $d = \sup_{|t' \leq t} \frac{Y(t')}{Y_c}$ if $d < 1$ otherwise $d = 1$

The critical energy Y_c equals Y_d for a unit value of d . It has been related to the experimental parameters of Fracture Mechanics : G_{Ic} , G_{IIc} and G_{IIIc} . Identification is done through these parameters.

RELATION BETWEEN TWO APPROACHES OF DELAMINATION : DAMAGE MECHANICS AND FRACTURE MECHANICS.

The comparison has been done on a D.C.B specimen with two elastic layers under a pure mode I loading.

The calculation uses Reissner's plate theory, under the assumption of plane strain state in the (N_1, N_2) plane. Thus, the displacements in the domain $\Omega = \Omega^+ \cup \Omega^-$ are written under the following form :

$$U = (u(x) - z v(x)) N_1 + w(x) N_2$$

The equilibrium equation of this problem is :

$$\nabla U^* \text{ symmetric} \quad \int_{\Omega} \text{Tr} (\sigma \varepsilon(U^*)) d\Omega + \int_{\Gamma} \sigma_{33} [U^*] d\Gamma = 2 P w^*(0)$$

and the constitutive relations are :

$$\sigma = \mathbb{K}_e \varepsilon \text{ in } \Omega \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_{33} = k_0 (1-d) [w] \text{ in } \Gamma$$

The condition for propagation is obtained from an instability condition reached for $d=1$.

On the other hand, G_{Ic} is calculated from the definition of G . For a long enough crack, it is possible to show that : $G_{Ic} \neq 2Y_c$

A similar result has been obtained for the second mode. Within this frame work, Fracture Mechanics appears as a simplified tool for delamination study in the case of established front and elastic layers ¹.

DAMAGE MECHANICS FOR THE ANALYSIS OF DELAMINATION IN THE VICINITY OF A HOLE.

Implementation of the above mechanical behaviour in a computer program to study the initiation and propagation in the vicinity of an initially circular hole is partially presented below ¹.

1. Formulation of the problem

The analysis is restricted to the vicinity of the edges in the domain Ω , where the three-dimensional effects are significant. A link with the solution obtained by a "shell" computation is made on the $\partial_1 \Omega$ area through given displacement U_d , the load F_d is imposed on the $\partial_2 \Omega$ area.

The problem to be solved is :

Find $(\sigma, \varepsilon) / \forall U^* \in \mathcal{U} = \{ U / U \text{ regular and } U|_{\partial_1 \Omega} = U_d(t) \}, \forall t \in [0, T]$

$$\int_{\Omega} \text{Tr} (\sigma \varepsilon(U^*)) d\Omega + \sum_{\Gamma}^{n-1} \int_{\Gamma} \sigma N [U^*] d\Gamma = \int_{\partial_2 \Omega} F_d(t) U^* dS$$

and (σ, ε) satisfies the constitutive non-linear relations in Ω and in Γ .

2. Examples

(1) Elastic computation

Results are given in elasticity, with an exemple of a structure $(0,45,-45,90)_S$. The hole is loaded by a radial pressure and the $\partial_1 \Omega$ area is built in. These results were obtained through a semi-analytical method with use of (i) the conjugate gradient method with conditioner and (ii) the Fast-Fourier-Transform. An axially symmetric conditioned operator is used to solve non axially symmetric problems.

. Fig.1 shows the displacements in band B at 0° . Fig.2 shows the peeling stress in this band at the $(90^\circ, 90^\circ)$ interface at the most loaded interface. This computation was made in 64 bands wick represented about 100000 degrees of freedom for the whole problem. It needed 25 iterations.

Fig.1

Fig.2

(2) Non-linear computation

A first example of a structure ($0^\circ, 90^\circ$) loaded in pure mode I is given. The displacement is imposed under the form $U(r=0) = t.U_0$. Fig.3 shows the exterior force work divided by t , with respect to t . This curve allows to predict through a global instability condition the delamination initiation and on which Gauss point it happens. Fig.4 shows the evolution of the peeling stress at this Gauss point.

Fig.3

Fig.4

A SIMPLIFIED METHOD FOR LAMINATE DELAMINATION

A low numerical cost study is now considered ⁴. Damage Mechanics allows to propose simplified criteria based on elastic calculations. In a finite element scheme, the degradation evolution is taken into account by modifying the elementary stiffnesses. The edge is assumed straight, thus the problem is reduced to a band. The laminate composite is modeled by a stacking of elastic layers bonded by damageable interface.

On an interface, as above : $\sigma N = k_1 [U_1] N_1 + k_2 [U_2] N_2 + k_3 [U_3] N_3$

The behaviour is elastic brittle.

$k_i \rightarrow +\infty$ perfect interface

$k_i = 0$ degraded interface, there is debonding.

1. Numerical solving.

In a finite element scheme, the problem to be solved is :

$$\mathbb{K} X = F$$

\mathbb{K} : global stiffness matrix, \mathbb{K} can be written under the following form :

$$\mathbb{K} = \mathbb{K}_0 + \tilde{\mathbb{K}}$$

\mathbb{K}_0 : global rigidity matrix of the layers ; $\tilde{\mathbb{K}}$: global rigidity matrix of the interfaces.
 Thus \mathbb{K}_0 is a diagonal matrix by units constituted of stiffness matrices $(\mathbb{K}_0)_i$ (subscript i indicating the i^{th} layer). $\tilde{\mathbb{K}}$ is also a diagonal matrix by units.

The conjugate gradient with conditioner iterative method is used. It allows to parallelise the global computation on each layer. The \mathbb{K}_0 matrix is the conditioner. Taking the special form of \mathbb{K}_0 into account for the j^{th} step the problem becomes :

$$(\mathbb{K}_0)_i (X^j)_i = (F^j)_i$$

At each step, the computation for each layer takes the forces applied by the adjacent layers into account .

2. Delamination analysis

The present answers to delamination initiation problem are limited. Nevertheless a first approach due to NUISMER and WHITNEY ¹⁰ is reported. It consists in a comparison between a reference quantity S^* with a critical value S_c . S^* is calculated at the distance a^* from the edge for each interface, especially where the stresses are not singular.

Let : $\underline{S} = \text{Sup}_{\text{interfaces}} (S^*(a^*))$; The criterion is : initiation if $\underline{S} > S_c$, where S_c and a^* are material constants.

We propose to follow this approach by using Damage Mechanics and choosing S^* similar to Y_d (cf supra). Another approach for initiation is based upon Fracture Mechanics. The characteristic distance a^* can be considered as the length of an initial crack due to an existing macro defect on the interface.

Let : $\underline{G} = \text{Sup}_{\text{interfaces}} (G(a^*))$; The criterion is : initiation if $\underline{G} \geq G_c$.

In a first step, the critical energy release rate G_c is assumed to be the same on each interface. The material characteristics S_c and G_c are experimentally obtained. For fatigue loadings, they are identified by comparison with Woehler's curves. Then, propagation is analysed with Fracture Mechanics.

REFERENCES

1. Allix O., "Délaminage des structures composites par la mécanique de l'endommagement", Thèse de l'Univ. P. et M. Curie, 1989.
2. Allix O., Gilletta D., Ladevèze P., "Mechanical behaviour of elementary constituents of laminates", ICCM5 (1985), 1039-1057.
3. Allix O., Ladevèze P., Le Dantec E., Vittecoq E., "Damage Mechanics for composite laminates under complex loadings", IUTAM/ICM (1988).
4. Boisse P., Ladevèze P., Poss M., Rougee P., "A new large time algorithm for anisotropic plasticity", IUTAM/ICM (1988).
5. Daudeville L., "Post-processeur d'analyse à la rupture des composites stratifiés : Délaminage", Rap. int. n°89 (1989), LMT Cachan.
6. Dumont J.P., Ladevèze P., Poss M., Remond Y., "Damage Mechanics for 3D composites", Composite Structures, 8 (1987), 119-141.
7. Gilletta D., "Modélisation mécanique et identification de la couche élémentaire", Thèse de l'Univ. P. et M. Curie, 1985.
8. Hashin Z., "Failure criteria for unidirectional fiber composites", J. of Appl. Mech., 47 (1980).
9. Ladevèze P., "Sur la mécanique de l'endommagement des composites", JNC5 (1986), Pluralis, 667-683.
10. Nuismer R.J., Whitney J.M., ASTM STP 593 (1975), 117-142.